

CHILDREN IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION TEACH A SECOND LANGUAGE (FOREIGN LANGUAGE)

Jurayeva Zamiraxon Quchqarboyevna

The Fergana Branch of Tashkent University of Information

Technology, Assistant Teacher

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Abstract: Early detection of the abilities of preschool children, thereby helping them to develop their abilities, and creating the necessary conditions are important issues. It has been repeatedly emphasized by experts that early detection of abilities and attention to them will make a huge contribution to the development of human life in the future. Undoubtedly, every child is unique and has his own talent from birth.

Key words: children, pre-school, education, second language, foreign language.

If you want to teach a second language (English, Russian, etc.) to a preschooler, this will definitely be a very good decision. Therefore, teaching foreign languages to children in this period, i.e. from 5 to 10 years old, brings positive results. At this time, children are both physiologically and emotionally resilient. Even in our daily life, we have witnessed that young children learn and memorize various information very quickly. In the process of language learning, they have the ability to remember not only new words, but also whole phrases, sentences and sentences. They do not need any grammatical rules or any other explanation. Children speak in whole sentences without grammar and grammatical constructions.

Preschool children are able to quickly learn new words added to their vocabulary and pronounce them fluently. We can clearly see the proof of this in the case of bilingual families.

Early childhood is a period of active exploration of the world, acquisition of new information, and language learning. This period is the child's pre-school age. A healthy child with no speech impediment can speak his mother tongue easily at the age of 3-4. Early exposure to the mother tongue makes it easier and faster for a child to learn other languages.

The educator and pedagogue has a special role in this process. Naturally, in order for a child to master the language well, it is necessary to motivate, encourage, and trust him. Above, we said that the most effective period of language learning is the pre-school age. What should we pay attention to and how should we train?

The important thing is that the child should not get bored during the study. He should like it. Classes should not exceed 30-35 minutes. Let the child take language training as a game process. Hyperactivity in children is not noticeable and the pedagogue can focus on the child.

From a psychological point of view, a child of this age does not have the "I'm going to say the wrong thing" attitude that adults have. Children speak quickly without thinking. This is the main communication process in speech. In adults, grammar and translation are dominant and this is a barrier. Preschool children, on the contrary, tend to speak faster, they do not have such stereotypes. Since the children's speech in their mother tongue is not yet fully developed, they accept another language as their own. How do we do this in a child:

1. Arousing desire in children (motivation);
2. Approach training through games;
3. Using memory exercises;
4. Memorizing songs and poems;
5. Working in harmony with imagination and visual activities;
6. Promotion, etc.

In the process of language teaching, a child is taught not only a foreign language, but also the culture, famous people, and architecture of those countries. In the child, this information helps to form feelings of mutual solidarity and respect. Along with knowing the language, it will help him in his development as a person. In pre-school educational organizations, project methods are used in children's language learning from 4 to 5 years old. Communicative method, that is, it is a method of communication. In this, the child learns to think and think in a foreign language. There are various interactive methods for teaching preschool children. Including:

1. Associative method, that is, the method of imagination.
2. "Aquarium" method
3. "Muzyorar"
4. "Division into groups"
5. "Aqliy hujum"
6. "Kim qayerda?"
7. "Mosaic"
8. "Ambulance"
9. "Stop Reading"
10. "Networks" (Cluster)
11. "Photo dictation"
12. "Chigil wrote" games

13. "Chain"
14. "Energizers"
15. "Everyone teaches everyone"
16. "Controversy"
17. "Continium", etc.
18. Audilingual and audiovisual method.
19. Oral speech and dialogues.
20. Learning and memorizing cartoons, songs, etc.

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